

Surgery – from the barber-surgeon era to modern times

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Abstract

Surgical practice dates back to ancient times, long before recorded history, and is characterized by its invasive methods for treating medical conditions. While early civilizations laid the foundation for understanding the human body, its functions, and anatomy, later generations refined these concepts, shaping modern medical theories. This article explores the historical role of barber-surgeons, their impact on the evolution of surgical practice, and the advancements that led to the establishment of surgery as a highly specialized medical discipline. Key milestones, such as the introduction of anesthesia, antiseptic techniques, and modern surgical education, will be examined, along with notable figures who transformed the field.

Keywords

History, surgery, barber-surgeon, modern era

Introduction

Surgery has its roots in the earliest days of human civilization. Over the centuries, significant advancements - spanning the Middle Ages, the Renaissance, and modern times - have transformed surgical methods and our understanding of them. ^[1] While many procedures are now regarded as routine, they developed through extensive trial and error, scientific discoveries, and technological innovations. ^[2] This article offers a historical overview of surgery, highlighting major milestones and the contributions of pioneering figures who shaped the field.

The barber-surgeon era

The term 'barber-surgeon' originated in 12th and 13th-century Europe, reflecting a profession that combined haircutting with minor surgical procedures. Historically, barbers also provided medical services such as bloodletting, wound

treatment, and tooth extractions. Unlike physicians, barber-surgeons did not receive formal academic training; instead, they acquired their skills through apprenticeship or personal experience. Consequently, surgical practices during this period varied widely in quality and effectiveness, often relying on the individual's practical knowledge rather than formal medical education. ^[3]

Despite the lack of formal education, barber-surgeons played a crucial role in medieval medicine. They were often the first point of contact for individuals seeking medical assistance, especially in rural areas where trained physicians were scarce. Barber-surgeons frequently accompanied military campaigns, treating wounds and performing amputations on the battlefield. Their practical experience in trauma management laid the groundwork for early surgical techniques. ^[4]

Barber-surgeons performed various procedures that went beyond basic wound care. They conducted trepanation (drilling into the skull to relieve pressure or treat injuries), amputations, and even early forms of cataract surgery.

Figure 1. Henry VIII and the Barber Surgeons by Hans Holbein (1497/1498–1543), <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5889157>.

Their work was often brutal due to the lack of anesthesia and knowledge about infection control. Furthermore, barber-surgeons were crucial in battlefield medicine, frequently performing emergency surgeries on wounded soldiers with limited resources. They executed amputations using basic saws and knives, relying on speed to lessen patient suffering. [4]

In 1540, King Henry VIII formalized the profession by merging the Barbers' Guild and the Surgeons' Guild into the Barber-Surgeons Company. This union helped regulate the practice, but it also created tensions between barber-surgeons and university-trained physicians. Over time, the rift between the two groups widened, culminating in the official separation of surgery from barbering in 1754. The newly formed Company of Surgeons eventually became the Royal College of Surgeons in 1800, marking the beginning of modern surgical education and regulation. [5]

Notable individuals of the barber-surgeon era

During this period, surgical knowledge largely drew upon anatomical theories inherited from ancient Greek and Roman sources. However, the Renaissance ignited a renewed interest in direct anatomical study, with Andreas Vesalius (1514–1564) leading the charge. Often referred to as the father of modern anatomy, Vesalius transformed the field with his groundbreaking work, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica*. In this text, he systematically challenged and corrected

long-standing anatomical misconceptions, including errors propagated by Galen, thereby establishing the foundation for modern surgical understanding. [6]

Ambroise Paré (1510–1590), a French barber-surgeon, further advanced the field by introducing innovative techniques for wound care. In the 1530s, while treating gunshot wounds, he ran out of boiling oil, the standard but extremely painful treatment to cauterize wounds. In desperation, he prepared an alternative mixture of egg yolk, rose oil, and turpentine. To his astonishment, the patients treated with his improvised remedy healed better and experienced less pain than those who received the traditional method. [6] This event led Paré to advocate for more humane surgical practices, significantly influencing wound care in medicine. He rejected the traditional practice of cauterizing wounds with boiling oil, instead championing the use of ligatures to control bleeding. This method significantly improved patient survival rates and marked a substantial shift toward more humane surgical practices. [7]

John Hunter (1728–1793), an anatomist and surgeon, underscored the importance of scientific observation and experimental research in surgery. He conducted extensive studies on comparative anatomy and developed new surgical techniques based on empirical evidence. [8] He was known for his daring approach to medical science, often experimenting on himself. In one of his most famous cases, he deliberately infected himself with syphilis and gonorrhea to study the progression of the diseases firsthand. His meticulous documentation of the symptoms and effects contributed significantly to the understanding of venere-

Figure 2. A Barber and a Surgeon Attending to Soldiers, by a follower of Hieronymus Janssens (1624–1693), https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:A_barber_and_a_surgeon_attending_to_soldiers._Oil_painting_b_Wellcome_V0023491.jpg.

al diseases, though at great personal risk. Hunter's contributions helped elevate surgery from a trade to a respected medical profession, influencing generations of surgeons to embrace a more systematic approach to patient care.^[8] The results of his experiments with animals, the specimens and the collection of his curiosities were held in a museum, where they were being learning objectives, but even to this day, some of them are reserved and could be seen in the Hunterian Museum in London.^[7]

Hans von Gersdorff (1455–1529), a German barber-surgeon, became famous for his work on battlefield medicine, particularly in amputation surgery. He authored *Feldbuch der Wundartzney* (Field Book of Surgery), a manual filled with detailed illustrations and descriptions of surgical techniques. His book became one of the most influential medical texts of the 16th century. His meticulous illustrations, including depictions of amputation techniques, served as a reference for future generations of surgeons, emphasizing the importance of proper wound care and treatment on the battlefield.^[9]

The need for more – the Royal College of Surgeons and new discoveries

The establishment of the Royal College of Surgeons in 1800 marked a turning point in surgical education and professionalization. By the 19th century, surgeons received more advanced training through formal medical schools, which enabled them to perform increasingly complex procedures. Several key discoveries during this period dramatically improved surgical outcomes.

The introduction of anesthesia

In 1846, dentist William Morton successfully demonstrated the use of ether as an anesthetic during surgery, ushering in a transformative era for surgical practice. The introduction of anesthesia allowed for pain-free operations, significantly

Figure 3. The First Operation Under Ether by Robert Hinckley (1882–1893), <https://collections.countway.harvard.edu/onview/items/show/26609>.

reducing patient distress and the risk of traumatic shock. Additionally, it enabled surgeons to perform more intricate procedures with greater precision, as they were no longer constrained by the urgency imposed by an awake and suffering patient. ^[6]

Antiseptic and Aseptic Techniques

Joseph Lister (1827–1912) revolutionized surgery by introducing antiseptic techniques. Inspired by Louis Pasteur's germ theory, Lister utilized carbolic acid (phenol) to sterilize surgical instruments and disinfect wounds. His methods significantly decreased postoperative infections, paving the way for modern aseptic practices. Subsequent advancements in sterilization, including the use of autoclaves and sterile gloves, further enhanced surgical safety. ^[6]

The Evolution of Modern Surgery

As medicine advanced, surgery became increasingly specialized. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, new fields

emerged, such as neurosurgery, cardiac surgery, and orthopedics. The development of imaging technologies, including X-rays and later MRI scans, improved surgeons' ability to diagnose and treat conditions with greater accuracy. ^[10]

The introduction of laparoscopic and robotic-assisted surgery in the late 20th century further transformed the field. Minimally invasive techniques reduced recovery times, minimized scarring, and improved patient outcomes. Today, robotic surgery enables unprecedented precision, allowing complex procedures to be performed with minimal human error. ^[10]

Conclusion

From the 17th century onward, surgery underwent significant advancements driven by scientific discoveries and technological innovations. By the 18th century, the growing complexity of surgical procedures required a clear distinction between surgery and barbering, which led to the professionalization of the field. Surgeons began to receive formal medical education, enhancing their status and refining their techniques. What was once a crude and dan-

gerous practice transformed into a precise and life-saving discipline. The legacy of barber-surgeons remains evident in modern surgical traditions, reflecting both historical influences and contemporary advancements. Today, surgery continues to evolve, supported by cutting-edge technology and a greater understanding of human biology. From robotic-assisted procedures to regenerative medicine, the future of surgery promises even greater opportunities for innovation and improved patient care.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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